

Deliverable D5.2 (D20)

Supervisory Board (Revised)

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The RNAct project

RNAct is a EU-MSCA ITN project with as research aim the design of novel **RNA recognition motif (RRM)** proteins for exploitation in synthetic biology and bio-analytics. We use **computational approaches** to analyse proteins and RNA, and test newly designed RRM in large-scale experiments. Viable RRM are studied with integrative **structural biology**, and will be applied in **synthetic biology** and in **bio-analytics**.

See <http://rnact.eu/> for more information.

Project partners

(Coordinator)

(Academic)

(Commercial)

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About this document

This reports deliverable D5.2 (D20) of the RNAct MSCA-ITN project. It was prepared by:

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V 1.0	11/3/2019	Final version	Wim Vranken and Aitor Sánchez (VUB)
V 1.1	23/8/2019	Revision; representative of RV updated	Wim Vranken and Aitor Sánchez (VUB)
V 1.2	28/11/2019	Revision; subcommittee deputy managers and ESR representative added	Wim Vranken and Aitor Sánchez (VUB)

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Supervisory and Management Boards

The supervisory board is the main decision-making body and will ensure centralised management with democratic and transparent decision processes. All supervisory meetings will be reported two months in advance with an agenda provided one week before the meeting, and meeting minutes within one week after the meeting.

The Management and Supervisory board members, as well as subcommittee managers, were officially appointed and installed, with the first supervisory board meeting having taken place on 31st of January 2019. For independent input, three external advisors covering at least the protein design, protein dynamics, and synthetic biology fields will be appointed. Each advisor will be invited to one meeting. We will endeavor to engage experts local to the meeting location whenever possible.

The supervisory board consists of the following members:

Name	Legal entity short name
Network Coordinator (NC) and Deputy Coordinator (DC)	
Wim Vranken (NC)	VUB
Michael Sattler (DC)	HMGU
Beneficiaries	
Isaure Chauvot de Beauchene	CNRS
Guillermo Rodrigo	CSIC
Jos Buijs	RV*
Tommaso Martelli	GIO
Ulrich Rant	DBS
Partners	
André Matagne	ULg
Malika Smaïl-Tabbone	UL
Helena Danielson	UU
Marco Fragai	UF
Carmelo López	UPV
Martin Zacharias	TUM
Program Manager (PM)	
Aitor Sánchez	VUB
RNAct ESR (to be selected by ESR peers)	
Jose Gavalda (ESR 1)	VUB
External Members	
One per meeting, drawn from local experts (to be defined)	-

* RIAB in the Consortium Agreement.

The management board is executive, and ensures the operation of the project and the implementation of supervisory board decisions. The management board reviews the project activities to ensure alignment with the network goals and monitors the progress against the milestones and deliverables defined in the description of activities. The management board also supports reporting to the EC, guarantees a smooth flow of information to the NC and executes the instructions from the EC and the supervisory board. The management board meets approximately every 7 months during the network-wide events, with intermediate online meetings possible if called by the NC. The management board is composed of the following members:

Name	Legal entity short name
Wim Vranken (NC and Leader WP 4,5, and 6)	VUB
Michael Sattler (DC and Leader WP 1)	HMGU
Aitor Sánchez (PM and Dissemination Subcommittee Manager)	VUB
Isaure Chauvot de Beauchene (Leader WP2 and Data Management Subcommittee Manager)	CNRS
Guillermo Rodrigo (Leader WP3)	CSIC
Eva Schlosser (Training Subcommittee Manager)	HMGU
Tommaso Martelli (Research Subcommittee Manager)	GIO

Subcommittees

Four subcommittees focused on training, research, dissemination and data management were assembled during the kick-off meeting on 31st of January 2019. These are composed of the subcommittee manager and the WP leaders, and will meet online typically bimonthly to follow up intermediate issues that require more focused attention. WP leaders involved but who may not be always present will be invited if their input is required.

Name	Legal entity short name
Training Subcommittee	
Eva Schlosser (Subcommittee Manager)	HMGU
Jos Buijs (Subcommittee Deputy Manager)	RV
Wim Vranken	VUB
Dissemination Subcommittee	
Aitor Sánchez (Subcommittee Manager)	VUB
Joel Roca (ESR 2; Subcommittee Deputy Manager)	VUB
Wim Vranken	VUB
Research Subcommittee	
Tommaso Martelli (Subcommittee Manager)	GIO
Michael Sattler	HMGU
Isaure Chauvot de Beauchene	CNRS
Guillermo Rodrigo	CSIC
Wim Vranken	VUB

Data Management Subcommittee	
Isaure Chauvot de Beauchene (Subcommittee Manager)	CNRS
Prof. Marie-Dominique Devignes (Subcommittee Deputy Manager)	CNRS
Prof. Malika Smail-Tabbone (Subcommittee Deputy Manager)	CNRS/UL
Wim Vranken	VUB